

Recent Publications

Ludwig Wittgenstein
Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus

OXFORD WORLD'S CLASSICS

Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus

Ludwig Wittgenstein

Michael Beaney

Oxford World's Classics

- Fresh translation of one of the most influential philosophical texts of the twentieth century.
- Michael Beaney's fluent and accurate translation takes account of Wittgenstein scholarship from the last five decades.
 - Accompanied by introductory essays and detailed explanatory notes to guide the reader through this enigmatic text.

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Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus

Ludwig Wittgenstein

Curatori: Pasquale Frascolla, Luigi Perissinotto

“La filosofia non è una dottrina,” sostiene Ludwig Wittgenstein, “ma un’attività.” Nel suo unico lavoro filosofico pubblicato in vita, Wittgenstein indica come obiettivo della filosofia la chiarificazione logica dei pensieri e si propone di mostrare l’insensatezza dei problemi della metafisica attraverso l’analisi logico-semantica. Partendo dai principi generali del simbolismo, formulati nella

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cosiddetta “teoria raffigurativa del linguaggio”, l’autore arriva a identificare il significato di una proposizione con le sue condizioni di verità. Da questo nucleo discende coerentemente la spiegazione della natura della verità logica, dell’inferenza e della probabilità. Uno degli aspetti salienti dell’opera sta nel fatto che i principi che fissano i limiti di ciò che si può dire sensatamente collocano oltre quei limiti, non solo la metafisica, ma la sfera dell’etica, dell’estetica e della credenza religiosa: su tutto ciò, secondo la perentoria ingiunzione di Wittgenstein che conclude l’opera, “si deve tacere”. In questa edizione, con testo tedesco a fronte, i due curatori offrono una nuova traduzione che libera il testo dal tono solenne e oracolare delle precedenti traduzioni italiane e contribuisce a gettar luce su alcuni passi di difficile interpretazione.

The Priority of Propositions. A Pragmatist Philosophy of Logic

María José Frápolli

This monograph is a defence of the Fregean take on logic. The author argues that Frege’s projects, in logic and philosophy of language, are essentially connected and that the formalist shift produced by the work of Peano, Boole and Schroeder and continued by Hilbert and Tarski is completely alien to Frege’s approach in the *Begriffsschrift*. A central thesis of the book is that judgeable contents, i.e. propositions, are the primary bearers of logical properties, which makes logic

embedded in our conceptual system. This approach allows coherent and correct definitions of logical constants, logical consequence, and truth and connects their use to the practices of rational agents in science and everyday life.

Wittgenstein and Aesthetics

Hanne Appelqvist

argues that aesthetics broadly conceived plays a significant role in Wittgenstein's philosophy. In doing so, it draws on the interpretative tradition that emphasizes affinities between Wittgenstein's thought and Kant's philosophy. Following the chronology of Wittgenstein's philosophical work, this Element addresses Wittgenstein's early equation between ethics and aesthetics, his middle-period discussion on the normative character of aesthetic judgments and the possibility of their justification, and his

later comparison between language and music. As a whole, it traces a continuous line of thought pertaining to a non-conceptual form of encounter with reality, which is developed in close conjunction with aesthetics and contributes to Wittgenstein's understanding of language and the method of philosophy throughout his career.

Intercultural Understanding After
Wittgenstein

Edited by Carla Carmona

David Perez-Chico

Chon Tejedor

Anthem Studies in Wittgenstein

This volume addresses, from a Wittgensteinian perspective, the philosophical question of how to understand other cultures. We approach this question in a manner that emphasises the connection between its epistemological, ethical and political aspects, bringing into discussion Wittgensteinian and other cultural and philosophical traditions, notably from the West African Yoruba community, Japan, China and India. The book is therefore not just about intercultural understanding, but also brings together, under the umbrella of Wittgensteinian philosophy, a plurality of cultural voices and philosophical cultures, and sets out to develop an approach to the question of intercultural understanding that emphasises the connection between its epistemological, ethical and political aspects.

Wittgenstein's Philosophy in 1929

Edited By Florian Franken Figueiredo

The book explores the impact of manuscript remarks during the year 1929 on the development of Wittgenstein's thought. Although its intention is to put the focus specifically on the manuscripts, the book is not purely exegetical. The contributors generate important new insights for understanding Wittgenstein's philosophy and his place in the history of analytic philosophy.

Limits of Intelligibility

Issues from Kant and Wittgenstein

Edited By Jens Pier

The chapters in this volume investigate the question of where, and in what sense, the bounds of intelligible thought, knowledge, and speech are to be drawn. Is there a way in which we are *limited* in what we think, know, and say? And if so, does this mean that we are *constrained*—that there is something beyond the ken of human intelligibility of which we fall short? Or is there another way to

think about these limits of intelligibility—namely, as *conditions* of our meaning and knowing anything, beyond which there is no specifiable thing we cannot do?

Wittgenstein on Religious Belief

Genia Schönbaumsfeld

Wittgenstein published next to nothing on the philosophy of religion and yet his conception of religious belief has been both enormously influential and hotly contested. In the contemporary literature, Wittgenstein has variously been labelled a fideist, a non-cognitivist and a relativist of sorts. This Element shows that all of these readings are misguided and seriously at odds, not just with what Wittgenstein says about religious belief,

but with his entire later philosophy. This Element also argues that Wittgenstein presents us with an important 'third way' of understanding religious belief – one that does not fall into the trap of either assimilating religious beliefs to ordinary empirical or scientific beliefs or seeking to reduce them to the expression of certain attitudes.

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